

Bridging Complexity and Usability: The DAVE Visual Execution Environment for AI/ML Pipelines

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Abstract—The growing adoption of AI/ML and data analytics pipelines in industrial and research settings has increased the demand for accessible, user-centred tools for pipeline management. While existing orchestration platforms provide mechanisms for execution tracking, they often expose complex execution information in ways that are difficult to interpret, limiting their usability. This paper presents the Data Analytics and Visualization Environment (DAVE) Execution Environment, a user-centred interface designed to support the execution, monitoring, and debugging AI/ML and ETL pipelines within the DAVE framework. The proposed approach is grounded in principles of visual clarity, task-level observability, and progressive information disclosure, enabling users to interpret pipeline behaviour and diagnose issues more effectively. The solution has been validated across multiple pilots in different sectors, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving the accessibility and interpretability of pipeline execution for non-expert users. These results highlight the potential of combining visual representations with task-level inspection to bridge the gap between pipeline complexity and usability in no-code/low-code MLOps environments.

Keywords—*Pipeline Execution Monitoring, MLOps, Data Analytics, User Interface, Observability*

I. INTRODUCTION

In a world where vast amounts of data are generated daily from multiple sources, global data volumes are projected to exceed 500 zettabytes by 2029 [1]. This data is vital to help optimize processes, extract knowledge and, through key metrics and KPIs, support decision-making. Data Analytics is the process of collecting, transforming and studying it to generate insights [2].

Extract, Load, Transform (ETL), Extract, Transform, Load (ELT), and AI/ML pipelines are among the most widely used approaches in Data Analytics. Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) are widely adopted for the orchestration, scheduling, execution and monitoring of these pipelines [3] [4]. By breaking down complex workflows into smaller, manageable chunks, called tasks, DAGs enable an easy monitoring of such pipelines and produce very detailed metadata and logs of the processes within the pipelines, critical for observability and effective debugging.

The Data Analytics and Visualization Environment (DAVE) is an open-source MLOps framework that uses a no-code/low-code approach to AI/ML and Data processing

workflows [5]. Developed and evolved within the frame of European projects such as the Vessel-AI [6], I4Q [7], and most recently the AI-DAPT [8] and MaaSAI [9], DAVE provides pre-built blocks of code, called Operators, that perform a variety of tasks, such as data cleaning, transformation and analysis, as well as model training algorithms with customizable parameters. These operators create an abstraction layer over the creation of these pipelines that allow non-expert users to build AI/ML and ETL pipelines. To create a pipeline, the user drags and drops these blocks to a canvas in the User Interface (UI) and connects them in order of execution.

Following pipeline design, a clear separation between design and execution environments becomes necessary to support effective monitoring and management of pipeline execution runs. A streamlined, accessible interface is required, enabling users to execute, monitor, and troubleshoot the existing pipeline through a unified platform, eliminating the need for auxiliary tools to perform these functions. The DAVE Execution Environment is proposed to address this need, providing a standalone interface where the user can manage pipeline executions, including manual triggering of runs, monitoring execution states, deleting previous runs, and visualizing the data and logs generated by each task in the pipeline. The UI should be intuitive and easy to navigate, presenting the current status of the running pipeline in a clear and accessible manner. Additionally, it should also present comprehensive access to pipeline metadata and execution details, supporting users in the process of debugging the pipeline.

The main technical contribution of this paper is in the integration of backend execution monitoring into the no-code/low-code abstraction layer of DAVE. Rather than exposing users directly to Airflow-specific concepts such as DAG runs, task instances, and backend metadata, the Execution Environment maps these execution entities back to DAVE Operators, which are the same abstractions used during pipeline design. This enables users to monitor execution state, inspect logs, and access operator-generated data at the operator level. The contribution therefore lies not only in providing a visual interface, but in preserving traceability between pipeline design and execution while supporting a progressive debugging workflow from run-level status, to operator-level failure localization, to logs and data inspection.

This paper presents the design and implementation of the DAVE Execution Environment and is structured as follows. Section II provides a literature review of the framework used and existing solutions for data and AI/ML pipeline creation, execution and monitoring and their corresponding execution monitoring UIs. Section III clarifies the design and implementation approach, while Section IV details the implementation of the Execution Environment, including the technologies and frameworks used, and early validation results. Section V presents the concluding remarks and future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the context of no-code/low code approaches to AI/ML pipeline creation and execution, a user interface that provides key information at a glance, such as execution status and results, is essential for facilitating effective tool usage. Access to this information is important when trying to debug errors in the pipeline, and the way this information is presented can affect the capability of the user to understand and fix these errors. Existing research emphasizes the importance of aiding the users in the process of debugging a pipeline and suggests “*visualizing messages that provide cues on the possible issues and provide actionable guidance*” [10].

A. Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)

DAGs are widely adopted in various fields of Data Engineering, including ETL/ELT pipelines, workflow orchestration, data processing pipelines and AI/ML pipelines [3] [4], to visually represent them [11] as it reduces fragile “glue code” by providing standardized orchestration for ML pipelines, which improves scalability, maintainability, and interoperability between different pipeline components and systems [12]. DAGs are used due to their capacity to break the complex processes into manageable tasks that can be organized to run in the correct order [3]. To represent a pipeline, a DAG contains the following elements:

- **Nodes**, which represent tasks in the pipeline.
- **Edges** that represent dependencies between tasks. A task connected by an edge to another cannot start before the second finishes running.
- **Parallel Branches** allow the pipeline to run parallel tasks with no dependencies at the same time.
- **Metadata and Logs** track the status and results of the execution of pipelines, providing observability over the pipeline and the ability to debug it.

Directed Acyclic Graph, as the name implies, has three properties [3]:

- **Directed** implies directionality, meaning that every edge points from one node to another, indicating a flow of information and/or dependency, e.g. if a task B depends on task A, the edge points from A to B.
- **Acyclic** means that the graph cannot contain cycles, as containing cycles could lead to tasks running indefinitely and conflicting dependencies.
- **Graph** refers to the structure of nodes and edges, where nodes represent tasks and edges represent the relationships between the nodes.

B. Existing Solutions

Existing tools that leverage the concept of DAGs to orchestrate pipelines include Apache Airflow [13], Apache Beam [14], and Kubeflow [15], while other solutions such as n8n [16] employ similar graph-based concepts. Each is examined below.

Apache Airflow is an open-source platform for developing, scheduling, and monitoring AI/ML and data processing pipelines [13], built on a Python framework. To represent DAGs intuitively, Airflow provides a web-based User Interface for visualising, managing, and debugging workflows, rendering DAGs using the React Flow library, which enables interactive graph visualisation on a canvas [17]. Nodes are displayed as boxes showing basic task information, such as the task name and execution status, while edges are rendered as lines connecting each task to its dependencies. Pipelines are defined through a YAML configuration file specifying tasks, dependencies, start time, schedule, and other parameters. Once created, a pipeline appears on the main page, where users can inspect its structure, execution status, and other relevant details. While pipelines are typically scheduled to run automatically, manual execution is also supported. During a run, task statuses are reflected in the graph through colour changes, for example, a running task is highlighted in bright green, transitioning to dark green upon successful completion. For deeper insight into individual task execution, clicking on the corresponding node opens a set of tabs containing the execution logs.

Kubeflow is an open-source AI/ML pipeline platform built on Kubernetes, incorporating TensorFlow's TFX components [18] within its DAGs [19]. Much like Airflow, Kubeflow provides a User Interface with a graph-based representation of the pipeline and visual indicators of each task's status. Clicking on a node in the graph opens several tabs: a visualisation tab displaying model metrics or task data output, an Input/Output tab showing the task's inputs and outputs, and a logs tab presenting the execution logs [20].

Apache Beam is conceptually similar to Airflow but is oriented towards ETL/ELT pipelines for data processing. It can also be embedded within the other solutions discussed, functioning as a DAG nested inside a larger DAG [14] [21]. Unlike the other tools presented, Apache Beam does not include a dedicated User Interface and instead relies on external solutions such as Airflow, Kubeflow, or Apache Hop [22].

n8n [16] is another widely used solution that offers a comparable representation of AI/ML pipelines, referred to as workflows. Each task is represented as a node, with nodes connected to one another to form the workflow graph. Like Airflow, n8n supports both automatic and manual workflow execution and provides a list of past executions for a selected pipeline. Within each execution, users can inspect node statuses and retry failed runs. However, n8n operates under a proprietary, subscription-based model, a notable drawback compared to the open-source alternatives discussed above.

TABLE I. SOLUTIONS COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Feature	<i>Apache Airflow</i>	<i>Kubeflow</i>	<i>Apache Beam</i>	<i>n8n</i>	<i>DAVE Execution Environment</i>
UI type	Web dashboard (code-defined DAGs)	Web dashboard (Kubernetes-native)	None built-in — runner's UI only	Visual drag-and-drop canvas	Web Dashboard with visual canvas
Pipeline/job graph	Interactive DAG graph, click to inspect tasks	Directed step graph with cached status	Dataflow graph	Live canvas with real-time node highlighting	Interactive DAG graph, click to inspect task logs and data
Log access	Per-task, per-attempt logs in UI	Pod logs via kubectl or external aggregator	Via runner platform (Stackdriver, Flink, Spark)	Per-node input/output JSON in editor	Per task, per run in UI
Historical runs	Grid view: all runs × tasks, color-coded by state	Experiment tracker with run comparison	Job history via runner platform	Execution history table, full trace per row	List of runs in Pipeline Execution List component
Performance view	Gantt chart per run, shows bottlenecks	Per-step duration in pipeline graph	Per-step throughput (Dataflow); none on Direct runner	None built-in	Per Pipeline Execution metrics (Status, Start Date, End Date, etc.)
Metrics & alerts	Service Level Agreement (SLA) miss tracking and email alerts	Scalar metrics, confusion matrices, ROC curves	Built-in counters/gauges via SDK; runner-dependent display	None built-in — needs Prometheus/Grafana	No Alerts Basic performance metrics
Artifact / data inspection	XCom values per task	Artifact lineage browser, dataset/model tracking	None	Inline data payload inspector per node	Data Sample Inspector in Terminal Component
Manual intervention	Backfill, re-run, parameter override from UI	Re-run from UI; no backfill concept	Not applicable	Manual trigger; no partial re-run	Manual Trigger of Pipeline Execution
Aggregate analytics	Basic run counts in UI	Run comparison within an experiment	None	None — history pruned; no trend charts	Basic Row Count in the Data Tab of Terminal Component
Notable gap	No ML-specific metrics	No general-purpose log UI	No UI without a managed runner	No throughput/error rate charts; history retention limits	No Alerts
Availability	Open Source	Open Source	Open Source	Proprietary (Paid)	Open Source

Table I complements the previous discussion by comparing the selected solutions across the main features required for pipeline execution, monitoring, debugging, performance assessment, and data inspection. The comparison shows that existing tools provide strong but uneven support across these dimensions.

Although some provide robust support for pipeline orchestration and execution, they only partially address the combination of visual monitoring, intuitive interaction, detailed debugging support, and accessibility required in no-code/low-code AI/ML environments. Airflow and Kubeflow offer mature execution tracking, historical run management, task-level inspection, and performance-related view, but their interfaces remain closely tied to backend concepts and may be less approachable for non-expert users. Apache Beam provides powerful pipeline execution capabilities but does not provide a dedicated interface for execution monitoring. n8n offers a more accessible visual workflow environment with execution history and node-level data inspection at the cost of being proprietary. This gap motivates the development of the DAVE Execution Environment. Built on top of Airflow, DAVE is positioned as a visual and operator-centred solution for managing AI/ML pipeline executions, combining execution history, task-level logs, generated data inspection, manual triggering, and simplified interaction within a no-code/low-code context.

C. Related Approaches

Beyond existing orchestration platforms, recent research has increasingly highlighted the need for dedicated methods to support the monitoring and debugging of AI/ML pipelines during execution. Shankar and Parameswaran [23] argue that production ML systems require end-to-end observability, introducing *MLTrace* as a system capable of collecting execution traces, monitoring pipeline-specific metrics, and supporting interactive debugging. Their work emphasizes

that effective supervision of pipelines depends on continuous visibility over execution states and transitions, rather than static or post-hoc analysis. This reinforces the need for interfaces that enable users not only to monitor execution in real time, but also to actively manage it, including triggering and controlling pipeline runs. Such requirements motivate the inclusion of mechanisms for manual execution and real-time status monitoring as core functionalities of execution environments.

Complementary research further highlights the importance of associating execution behaviour with task-level information and intermediate results. Grafberger et al. [24], through *mlinspect*, demonstrate how extracting DAG representations and propagating metadata across pipeline steps enables the identification of data-related issues during execution. This approach underlines the importance of presenting execution information at the level of individual tasks, including logs, metadata, and data outputs, to support effective debugging. Ono et al. [25] propose *PipelineProfiler*, a visual analytics tool that facilitates the exploration and comparison of complex pipelines through interactive representations. These works collectively point to the need for visual structures that reflect pipeline topology, where task dependencies and execution states can be easily interpreted. Such insights support the design of a canvas-based interface, where pipelines are represented as graphs with task-level status indicators, enabling users to quickly identify failures and understand execution flow.

Finally, the literature also emphasizes the importance of organizing execution information in a way that supports both high-level monitoring and detailed inspection. Survey work on visual analytics for machine learning [26] highlights that users benefit from combining overview and detail-on-demand paradigms when interacting with complex systems. In the context of pipeline execution, this translates into the

Fig. 1. Airflow User Interface

need for mechanisms that provide both an overview of multiple runs and access to detailed execution data. This justifies the inclusion of a list of executions, enabling users to track and select different pipeline runs, as well as a terminal-like component, where detailed information such as logs, metadata, and intermediate data can be inspected. Together, these elements support a complete workflow for monitoring (status overview and execution history) and debugging (task-level inspection and data analysis).

Despite the progress in existing research, there remains a lack of integrated, user-centered environments that combine run-level monitoring, operator-level execution state, task-specific logs, generated data inspection, and simplified interaction within no-code/low-code AI/ML systems. This gap motivates the design of the DAVE Execution Environment presented in the following section.

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

Building on the limitations identified in existing solutions and the requirements derived from the literature, this section presents the design and implementation of the DAVE Execution Environment. The interface design sub-section outlines and justifies the key design decisions, providing a clear rationale for the chosen structure and functionality. The implementation approach sub-section offers a concise overview of the development strategy, including the selection and integration of the system's components.

A. Interface Design

The design of the Execution Environment is guided by the need to bridge the gap between the complexity of AI/ML pipeline execution and the usability requirements of non-expert users. As identified in Section II, existing solutions provide strong execution and monitoring capabilities but often expose information in ways that are difficult to interpret (see Fig. 1), particularly in no-code/low-code contexts. Since DAVE leverages Apache Airflow as the pipeline scheduling and execution engine, the UI of the DAVE Execution Environment is designed around the information provided by the Airflow API. As a result, the interface retains key elements found in the Airflow UI, namely a graph-based representation

of the running pipeline, colour-coded indicators of each Operator's execution state, a list of pipeline executions, and access to task-level logs.

The design of the DAVE Execution Environment is guided by three key principles: visual clarity, task-level observability, and progressive information disclosure.

Visual clarity is achieved through a graph-based representation of the pipeline, reflecting its underlying DAG structure. This enables users to understand the execution flow and task dependencies at a glance, reducing cognitive effort when interpreting pipeline behaviour. The use of color-coded states further supports rapid identification of running, completed, or failed tasks. **Task-level observability** ensures that detailed information is available for each Operator within the pipeline. Rather than limiting the interface to high-level execution states, the system provides access to logs, metadata, and, when applicable, intermediate data outputs generated during execution. This aligns with the need identified in the literature to associate execution behaviour with task-level information in order to effectively diagnose and debug pipeline issues. **Progressive information disclosure** combines overview and detail-on-demand interaction. Users are initially presented with a high-level view of pipeline executions and their current status and can progressively explore more detailed information by selecting specific executions or Operators. This approach reduces information overload while maintaining access to the full set of execution details required for debugging.

These principles are operationalized through three main components to present the necessary information clearly and intuitively: (i) the Canvas, which operationalizes visual clarity; (ii) the Terminal, which supports task-level observability; and (iii) the Pipeline Execution List, which enables progressive information disclosure.

These components were selected to support a progressive execution-management workflow. The execution list provides the run-level entry point, allowing users to select and compare pipeline executions. The canvas provides operator-level monitoring by synchronizing the visual state of each DAVE Operator with its corresponding backend execution state. The

terminal provides the diagnostic layer, where execution metadata, logs, and generated data can be inspected for the selected run or operator. Together, these components preserve the abstraction used during pipeline design while exposing the technical information required for monitoring and debugging.

B. Implementation Approach

Rather than being tightly coupled to the execution engine, the system is designed as an interaction layer that interfaces with Apache Airflow through its API, enabling access to execution metadata, task states, and logs while maintaining independence from the underlying orchestration logic. Fig. 2 presents a conceptual architecture of the Execution Environment, showing its interactions with external components: the Airflow API, used to fetch pipeline execution metadata and logs, and the Intermediate Storage, where data generated during execution is stored. The Airflow API acts as the primary source of truth for pipeline state and execution events, while the intermediate storage enables retrieval of task-level outputs required for inspection and debugging.

A central aspect of the implementation approach is the management of pipeline executions as independent entities. Each execution is treated with a distinct context, representing a specific instance of a pipeline run, which may be triggered either automatically through scheduling or manually by the user (e.g. through a simple button). Since a pipeline can have multiple executions, the system needs to provide a way to identify and select specific ones for inspection. This selection defines the scope of the information presented across the interface, ensuring that all components consistently reflect the state and data associated with the chosen execution. This is handled by the Pipeline Execution List component, which displays all runs of a given pipeline, and enables the user to select which to visualise.

Monitoring of pipeline execution is based on the continuous retrieval and update of task-level state information, enabling the interface to reflect execution progress as it occurs. As a pipeline executes, each task transitions through different states, and these changes must be made visible to the user in a timely and coherent manner. To provide the user with a visual representation of the execution status, a canvas-based interface must be integrated in the Execution Environment, where a representation of the pipeline can be visualized and its status updated in real time. The canvas should be an interactive interface where a graph representation of the pipeline is shown. In this graph, each Operator is represented as a block in the graph, whereas the connections between each Operator and the next is represented as a line between them. Taking inspiration from Airflow's own visual representation, the colour of each block

updates as the pipeline runs: a block turns light green when its Operator begins executing, dark green when it completes successfully, and red if it fails. By dynamically updating task states, the system enables users to identify the current execution point and detect failures or bottlenecks within the pipeline. This approach provides a direct link between the structural representation of the pipeline and its runtime behaviour, allowing users to quickly locate the source of execution issues and understand their impact within the overall workflow.

While the structural representation of the pipeline, provided by the Canvas helps identify where things went wrong, debugging often requires a closer look at individual Operators. This is supported by the Terminal component, which provides access to the pipeline configuration, Airflow's execution logs for each Operator, and, where applicable, a sample of intermediate data outputs. This integration of structural context and detailed execution data allows users to correlate pipeline structure, execution state, and task-level outputs, supporting a comprehensive debugging workflow.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

The DAVE Execution Environment was built using the React framework for web UI development, with the HeroUI [27] component library used to streamline implementation. HeroUI provides a set of ready-to-use React components that can be customised and styled to fit the specific needs of the tool. To retrieve pipeline execution data from Apache Airflow, such as execution status and logs, the Execution Environment communicates with Airflow's REST API.

A key implementation aspect is the mapping between DAVE Operators and Airflow execution entities. Each Operator displayed in the Canvas is associated with the corresponding Airflow task instance for the selected DagRun. This mapping enables task states retrieved from Airflow to be propagated to the visual operator representation and allows operator-specific logs and generated data to be accessed directly from the interface. As a result, users interact with execution information through DAVE's operator abstraction rather than through Airflow's lower-level execution model.

As described in the previous section, the interface is divided into three main components: the Canvas, the Pipeline Execution List, and the Terminal, as shown in Fig. 3.

The Canvas is built on the React Flow [17] library, a React-based tool for creating interactive node-based diagrams. Operators are defined as nodes and their connections as edges, forming an interactive graph where each Operator is displayed as a block. Each block includes identifying information such as the Operator name, type, and the technology powering it. In addition to these static elements, each block features an info button that opens a card with a description of the underlying algorithm, as well as buttons to open the logs and data for that specific Operator. To support real-time monitoring, and as specified in the implementation approach, the blocks are colour-coded according to each Operator's execution status. This information is streamed live from Airflow via a WebSocket connection, established when the user selects a pipeline execution.

Fig. 2. DAVE Execution Environment Architecture

Fig. 3. DAVE Execution Environment User Interface

The selection of pipeline executions is handled by the Pipeline Execution List component, which retrieves execution metadata from the Airflow API and maintains the list of available DagRuns for a given pipeline. Each execution is identified by its unique DagRun ID, which is used across the interface to query execution-specific data. The component also supports deletion of executions by issuing requests to the Airflow API and updating the list accordingly.

The Terminal provides detailed information about the pipeline, including execution metadata (from Airflow API), logs, and data generated by each Operator (from DAVE's Intermediate Storage). To support near real-time monitoring, log data is streamed using WebSocket connections to the relevant Airflow API endpoints, allowing logs to be updated dynamically in the Logs tab, as shown in Fig. 4(a).

For data inspection, the system queries the intermediate storage where outputs generated during execution are stored in collections indexed by DagRun ID and Operator identifier. To ensure responsiveness, only a subset of the data is retrieved and displayed in the Data view, shown in Fig. 4(b). This tab displays a 10-row sample of the data generated during execution.

Together, these three components give users a detailed yet accessible view of their pipeline executions, making it easier to spot and correct errors in the pipeline's construction.

A. Validation and Early Feedback

The implemented solution is currently being validated under the AI-DAPT and MaaSAI projects, across multiple pilots spanning from Manufacturing to Robotics, Energy and Health. In these pilots, users are employing DAVE to create, run, and monitor their custom AI/ML and data processing pipelines. This subsection presents the results of this validation, covering early feedback gathered from the partners of the projects during co-design, followed by a structured evaluation strategy addressing system-level performance and user-centred usability.

Early feedback during the solution co-design provided useful insights on both the technical behaviour of the

Execution Environment and its suitability for supporting pipeline execution monitoring in applied project contexts.

A recurring issue was identified in the Pipeline Execution List component. When deleting a past execution, clicking the delete icon would occasionally leave the entry visible in the list rather than removing it immediately. This could be bypassed by refreshing the page or retrying the deletion, but it remains to be addressed in future releases. A few other minor problems also surfaced, such as occasional interface freezing and failure to update pipeline statuses correctly. These were largely attributed to resource constraints, since running all DAVE components requires close to 16 GB of RAM, making it particularly prone to instability when deployed on edge devices or machines with limited resources, such as virtual machines or hosts with 16 GB of RAM or less. Nevertheless, none of these issues significantly hindered normal use of the Execution Environment, and users were still able to run and monitor their pipelines successfully.

To complement this early technical validation, a more structured validation is considered across two dimensions, in particular, system-level performance and user-centred usability. The objective is, therefore, not only to verify the technical correctness of the implementation, but also to assess whether the proposed interface helps users understand pipeline execution states, identify failures, and access relevant debugging information.

From a system perspective, the evaluation considers three representative pipelines with increasing complexity: (i) a simple linear pipeline, (ii) a branched pipeline with parallel operators, and (iii) a pipeline containing an intentionally failing operator. For each pipeline the evaluation measures execution status update latency, user's time to identify a failing operator, log retrieval latency, time required to display operator-level data samples, task completion rate, measuring whether users can utilise the Execution Environment to help diagnose a pipeline and successfully execute it, and number of interaction errors. These metrics were selected because they directly affect the user's ability to monitor executions in

```

Run Workflow Logs X
/home/airflow/.local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/dagfactory/dagfactory.py, line: 241, in: load_yaml_dags
/home/airflow/.local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/dagfactory/dagfactory.py, line: 185, in: generate_dags
/home/airflow/.local/lib/python3.12/site-packages/dagfactory/dagfactory.py, line: 162, in: build_dags
2026-03-03T17:48:20.509633Z - Loading /opt/airflow/dags/test-pipeline_dag.yaml
2026-03-03T17:48:20.535968Z - task_params непер обработки: {'op_kwarg': {'dataset': 'sample_dataset.csv'}, 'task_id': 'Data', 'dag': <DAG: test-pipeline>, 'python_callable': <function main at 0x777fa13074900>}
2026-03-03T17:48:20.556469Z - task_params непер обработки: {'op_kwarg': {'columns': 'first_name,last_name,city', 'mode': 'Remove'}, 'task_id': 'Filter-Cols', 'dag': <DAG: test-pipeline>, 'python_callable': <function main at 0x777fa130744a0>}
2026-03-03T17:48:20.576904Z - task_params непер обработки: {'op_kwarg': {'boosting_type': 'gbdt', 'colsample_bytree': 1, 'learning_rate': 0.1, 'max_depth': -1, 'min_child_samples': 20, 'min_child_weight': 0.001, 'min_split_gain': 0, 'model_name': 'test', 'n_estimators': 100, 'num_leaves': 31, 'subsample': 1, 'target_col': 'age'}, 'task_id': 'Model', 'dag': <DAG: test-pipeline>, 'python_callable': <function main at 0x777fa13074b80>}
2026-03-03T17:48:20.577680Z - DAG loaded: /opt/airflow/dags/test-pipeline_dag.yaml
2026-03-03T17:48:20.577680Z - Loading /opt/airflow/dags/test_dag.yaml
2026-03-03T17:48:20.600429Z - task_params непер обработки: {'op_kwarg': {'dataset': 'sample_dataset.csv', 'separator': ','}, 'task_id': 'Data', 'dag': <DAG: test>, 'python_callable': <function main at 0x777fa13074e00>}
2026-03-03T17:48:20.614238Z - task_params непер обработки: {'op_kwarg': {'columns': 'first_name,last_name,city', 'mode': 'Remove'}, 'task_id': 'Filter', 'dag': <DAG: test>, 'python_callable': <function main at 0x777fa13074f40>}
2026-03-03T17:48:20.661279Z - task_params непер обработки: {'op_kwarg': {'boosting_type': 'gbdt', 'colsample_bytree': 1, 'learning_rate': 0.1, 'max_depth': -1, 'min_child_samples': 20, 'min_child_weight': 0.001, 'min_split_gain': 0, 'model_name': 'test', 'n_estimators': 100, 'num_leaves': 31, 'subsample': 1, 'target_col': 'age'}, 'task_id': 'Model', 'dag': <DAG: test>, 'python_callable': <function main at 0x777fa13075080>}
2026-03-03T17:48:20.661626Z - DAG loaded: /opt/airflow/dags/test_dag.yaml
2026-03-03T17:48:20.751875Z - ['first_name', 'last_name', 'city']
2026-03-03T17:48:20.784991Z - Done. Returned value was: None

```

(a) Terminal's Logs Tab

ID (Int)	FIRST NAME (String)	LAST NAME (String)	AGE (Int)	CITY (String)
1	Alice	Johnson	28	New York
2	Brian	Smith	34	Chicago
3	Carla	Marinez	25	Los Angeles
4	David	Lee	42	Houston
5	Emma	Brown	31	Phoenix
6	Frank	Wilson	29	Philadelphia
7	Grace	Taylor	37	San Antonio
8	Henry	Anderson	45	San Diego
9	Isabella	Thomas	26	Dallas

(b) Terminal's Data Tab

Fig. 4. DAVE Execution Environment Terminal Component

near real time and to react to failures during pipeline execution. Average values, measured over 50 executions, are presented in table II.

TABLE II. EVALUATION METRICS

Metric	Results (Avg)
Execution status update latency	2.08s
Time to identify failing operator	~400 ms
Time to access Execution Logs	0.751s
Time to view Operator output data sample	1.343s
Task completion rate	TBD
Interaction Errors	TBD
User perception questionnaire	TBD

The user-centred usability evaluation is planned to be performed closer to the conclusion of the AI-DAPT and MaaSAI projects, as part of the broader validation and evaluation process of the project pilots. In that evaluation, users will be asked to complete a set of predefined tasks covering the main use cases of the interface: manually triggering a pipeline execution, identifying the current status of a running pipeline, locating the operator responsible for a failed execution, accessing the corresponding execution logs, and inspecting a sample of the data generated by an operator. For each task, the evaluation will record task completion rate, time to completion, number of interaction errors, and whether the user required assistance. After completing the tasks, short usability questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale will be used, covering perceived ease of use, clarity of the visual execution status, usefulness of the execution list, usefulness of the terminal, and confidence in identifying and diagnosing execution failures.

Finally, the current implementation also revealed broader architectural limitations. Since DAVE's orchestration layer is built on top of Apache Airflow, it is inherently constrained by what the Airflow API exposes, which limits the information that can be surfaced in the Execution Environment. In addition, Airflow also proved to be resource-intensive, with a local instance consuming upwards of 8 GB of RAM, a figure that can grow with the complexity of the pipelines being executed. Additionally, the absence of DAG versioning means that modified pipelines may cause older runs to be displayed incorrectly, either omitting removed operators or showing operators added in later versions.

B. Match and Contributions

This paper contributes to the ICE 2026 conference themes and IEEE TEMS research objectives through its focus on user-centered design of execution interfaces for AI/ML pipeline management, addressing critical challenges in digital transformation and innovation accessibility. The DAVE Execution Environment aligns strongly with the Digital Transformation for Competitiveness topic area, specifically *AI/ML in industrial processes and supply chains*. By providing an intuitive interface for managing AI/ML pipeline executions, this work enables organizations to deploy and monitor AI/ML workflows more effectively in production environments.

The Execution Environment directly addresses *System-level monitoring and diagnostics in cyber-physical and industrial systems* (related to the Preparedness, Readiness, Supervision, and Monitoring of Complex Systems topic). The three-component architecture, combining visual pipeline representation, execution history, and the integrated terminal, addresses the *Supervisory control architectures for adaptive and autonomous systems* topic. The real-time status updates, color-coded execution states, and integrated logging capabilities enable operators to perform *Crisis response, fault*

detection, and recovery in high-stakes environments, particularly when AI/ML pipelines are deployed in critical industrial applications.

The paper also contributes significantly to People, Skills, and Inclusive Transition, specifically *Human-centric AI and inclusive innovation ecosystems*. The no-code/low-code approach embodied in the DAVE platform democratizes access to AI/ML pipeline development and execution, reducing the technical expertise required to build and monitor sophisticated data analytics workflows. This supports *Workforce transformation for green and/or digital jobs* by enabling professionals without deep programming backgrounds to engage with AI/ML technologies, expanding the talent pool capable of contributing to digital transformation initiatives.

Additionally, within Generative AI for Industrial & Educational Intelligence, the Execution Environment contributes to Human-in-the-loop systems and explainability in high-impact industrial & educational contexts. The comprehensive logging, data visualization, and execution state monitoring features provide transparency into AI/ML pipeline operations, enabling users to understand and verify the behaviour of automated workflows, a critical requirement for trustworthy AI deployment in industrial settings.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The DAVE Execution Environment provides a UI that allows users to run, monitor and debug the execution of AI/ML and ELT pipelines, addressing the challenges identified in the management of complex pipeline workflows. By combining a graph-based representation of pipelines, execution history tracking, and task-level inspection capabilities, the proposed approach supports both high-level monitoring and detailed debugging of pipeline executions.

A key contribution of this work lies in the integration of visual clarity, task-level observability, and progressive information disclosure within a unified execution environment. These design principles, operationalized through the Canvas, Pipeline Execution List, and Terminal components, enable users to correlate pipeline structure, execution state, and task-level outputs, improving the interpretability and accessibility of pipeline execution, particularly for non-expert users in no-code/low-code contexts.

The implementation of the Execution Environment on top of the Apache Airflow demonstrates the feasibility of decoupling user interaction from the underlying orchestration layer, while still providing real-time access to execution state, logs, and data outputs. The results obtained across multiple industrial and research pilots indicate that the proposed approach facilitates pipeline monitoring and debugging, contributing to more efficient development and operation of AI/ML workflows. However, the use of Airflow as the underlying execution engine limits the information available in the Execution Environment to what is exposed by its API. Airflow also proved to be very resource-intensive, which posing challenges when deploying in resource-constrained environments such as edge devices. Current implementation still lacks support for features such as DAG versioning, which will enable the tool to be more accurate and flexible.

The limitations presented earlier motivate several directions for future work. The introduction of DAG versions

should resolve the misrepresentation of historical pipeline runs by associating each run with the version it was executed in, ensuring the correct blocks corresponding to the tasks that were in the pipeline at the time of execution are rendered. Additionally, the metadata tabs currently display all Airflow-related JSON data, much of which is irrelevant to the user. In the future, these should be streamlined to show only pertinent information, organized intuitively, such as start and end times in the Run tab, and schedule interval and tasks in the Workflow tab. The bugs outlined in Section IV should also be addressed to prevent disruptions to normal usage. Finally, a user evaluation study will be conducted with partners from the AI-DAPT project, gathering feedback on ease of use, UI clarity, and user perception.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the contribution of the European Commission-funded Horizon Europe research project AI-DAPT (Grant agreement ID: 101135826) and Horizon Europe research project MaaSAI (Grant agreement ID: 101177368) for the development and validation of the presented work.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Taylor, "Volume of data or information created, captured, copied and consumed worldwide from 2010 to 2029," 19 November 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/871513/worldwide-data-created/>.
- [2] M. Chen, "What Is Data Analytics? How It's Used & Practical Uses," 7 October 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oracle.com/europe/analytics/data-analytics/>.
- [3] M. Adhikari, T. Amgoth and S. N. Srirama, "A Survey on Scheduling Strategies for Workflows in Cloud Environment and Emerging Trends," New York, NY, USA, 2019.
- [4] M. E. Inzaugarat, "What is DAG? A Practical Guide with Examples," 21 November 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.datacamp.com/blog/what-is-a-dag>.
- [5] A. Grilo, P. Figueiras, B. Rêga, L. Lourenço, A. Khodamoradi, R. Costa and R. Jardim-Gonçalves, "Data Analytics Environment: Combining Visual Programming and MLOps for AI workflow creation," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)*, Funchal, Madeira Island, Portugal, 2024.
- [6] VesselAI Project Consortium, "About VesselAI," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://vessel-ai.eu/>.
- [7] I4Q Project Consortium, "I4Q Project Home Page," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.i4q-project.eu/>.
- [8] AI-DAPT Project Consortium, "AI-DAPT Project Home Page," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ai-dapt.eu/>.
- [9] MaaSAI Project Consortium, "MaaSAI - Empowering the manufacturing process through autonomous AI," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://maasai-project.eu/>.
- [10] Z. Zhou, J. Jin, V. Phadnis, X. Yuan, J. Jiang, X. Qian, K. Wright, M. Sherwood, J. Mayes, J. Zhou, Y. Huang, Z. Xu, Y. Zhang, J. Lee, A. Olwal, D. Kim, R. Iyengar, N. Li and R. Du, "InstructPipe: Generating Visual Blocks Pipelines with Human Instructions and LLMs," in *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, Yokohama, Japan, 2025.
- [11] A. Mbata, Y. Sripada and M. Zhong, "A Survey of Pipeline Tools for Data Engineering," *arXiv:2406.08335*, p. 18, 12 June 2024.
- [12] H. Hapke and C. Nelson, *Building Machine Learning Pipelines*, O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2020, pp. 8-9.
- [13] J. Yasmin, J. Wang, Y. Tian and B. Adams, "An Empirical Study of Developers' Challenges in Implementing Workflows as Code: A Case Study on Apache Airflow," *arXiv:2406.00180*, p. 45, 31 May 2024.

- [14] Apache Software Foundation, "Workflow Orchestration," 02 April 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://beam.apache.org/documentation/ml/orchestration/>.
- [15] E. Bisong, "Kubeflow and Kubeflow Pipelines," in *Building Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models on Google Cloud Platform*, Berkeley, CA, Apress, 2019, p. 671–685.
- [16] n8n, "Workflows," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.n8n.io/workflows/>.
- [17] xyflow Team, "Overview," 19 March 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://reactflow.dev/learn/concepts/terms-and-definitions>.
- [18] D. Baylor, E. Breck, H.-T. Cheng, N. Fiedel, C. Y. Foo, Z. Haque, S. Haykal, M. Ispir, V. Jain, L. Koc, C. Y. Koo, L. Lew, C. Mewald, A. N. Modi, N. Polyzotis, S. Ramesh, S. Roy, S. E. Whang, M. Wicke, J. Wilkiewicz, X. Zhang and M. Zinkevich, "TFX: A Tens or Flow-Based Production-Scale Machine Learning Platform," in *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, New York, NY, USA, 2017.
- [19] The Kubeflow Authors, "Overview (Kubeflow Pipelines)," 17 June 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/components/pipelines/overview/>.
- [20] The Kubeflow Authors, "Visualize Results in the Pipelines UI," 29 March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/components/pipelines/legacy-v1/sdk/output-viewer/>.
- [21] T. Akidau, R. Bradshaw, C. Chambers, S. Chernyak, R. J. Fernandez-Moctezuma, R. Lax, S. McVeety, D. Mills, F. Perry, E. Schmidt and S. Whittle, "The dataflow model: a practical approach to balancing correctness, latency, and cost in massive-scale, unbounded, out-of-order data processing," *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1792-1803, 2015.
- [22] Apache Software Foundation, "Visual Apache Beam Pipeline Design and Orchestration with Apache Hop," [Online]. Available: <https://beam.apache.org/case-studies/hop/>.
- [23] S. Shankar and A. G. Parameswaran, "Towards Observability for Production Machine Learning Pipelines," *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, vol. 15, no. 13, pp. 4015-4022, 2022.
- [24] S. Grafberger, P. Groth, J. Stoyanovich and S. Schelter, "Data distribution debugging in machine learning pipelines," *The VLDB Journal*, vol. 31, p. 1103–1126, 31 January 2022.
- [25] J. P. Ono, S. Castelo, R. Lopez, E. Bertini, J. Freire and C. Silva, "PipelineProfiler: A Visual Analytics Tool for the Exploration of AutoML Pipelines," *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, vol. 27, no. 02, pp. 390-400, 2021.
- [26] J. Yuan, C. Chen, W. Yang, M. Liu, J. Xia and S. Liu, "A survey of visual analytics techniques for machine learning," *Computational Visual Media*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 3-36, 2021.
- [27] NextUI Inc., "Introduction," [Online]. Available: <https://heroui.com/docs/react/getting-started>.
- [28] S. Sajid, A. Klironomos, E. Kharlamov, F. Hopfgartner and M. H. Gad-Elrab, "No-Code ML Pipeline Development: Leveraging knowledge graphs and language models," in *The Semantic Web: ESWC 2025 Satellite Events*, Portoroz, Slovenia, 2025.
- [29] Y. Zhou, Y. Yu and B. Ding, "Towards MLOps: A Case Study of ML Pipeline Platform," in *2020 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Engineering (ICAICE)*, Beijing, China, 2020.
- [30] M. Shahnawaz and M. Kumar, "A Comprehensive Survey on Big Data Analytics: Characteristics, Tools and Techniques," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 1-33, 2025.
- [31] C.-W. Tsai, C.-F. Lai, H.-C. Chao and A. V. Vasilakos, "Big data analytics: a survey," *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 2, no. 21, 2015.